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D4.3 Nanomaterials

Human/machine-readable provenance and persistence policies

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Lead Author (Org)	Iseult Lynch (UoB)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Thomas Exner (7P9-DE), Antreas Afantitis (NovaM)

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

AOP	Adverse Outcome Pathway
CDIF	Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GUPRI	Globally Unique Persistent and Resolvable Identifiers
IGSN	International Generic Sample Number
InChI	International Chemicals Identifier
NanoInChI	Extension of InChI to represent nanomaterials
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
PARC	Partnership for Assessment of the Risks of Chemicals
PID	Persistent Identifier
SSbD	Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design
UUID	Universal Unique Identifier

Executive summary

The WorldFAIR Nanomaterials Case study (WP04) has addressed several important topics including undertaking a mapping of the FAIR landscape for nanomaterials ([D4.1](#))¹ and development of best practice for FAIR nanoinformatics models ([D4.2](#))². D4.3, presented here, complements and extends the previous two deliverables focussing in particular on Provenance and Persistence of nanomaterials data, considering both human and machine actionable aspects. D4.3 addresses, in particular, FAIR principle R1.2 whereby *(Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance*, which is essential to enable re-use of data as it provides assurances to potential re-users as to where the data came from, how it was generated and for what purpose, and FAIR principle A2: *Metadata should be accessible even when the data is no longer available*, which is an essential aspect of ensuring provenance and persistence of data and its associated metadata.

The deliverable builds on work and best practice from:

- I. FAIR experts and FAIR-focussed projects (e.g., FAIRsFAIR³) on the role and importance of persistent identifiers, unique identifiers and resolvable identifiers (collectively persistent identifiers (PIDs), universal unique identifiers (UUIDs) or globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifiers (GUPRIs)) to support data provenance including a landscape mapping of the types of PIDs;
- II. research performed in the nanomaterials domain as a pilot project around persistent identifiers for nanomaterials themselves, bearing in mind their complexity (as both chemicals and particles) and dynamic nature whereby many of their properties are extrinsic and context-dependent;
- III. intensive discussions with other case studies from WorldFAIR, mainly Chemistry, Geochemistry, Biodiversity, Agricultural Biodiversity and Cultural Heritage; these were facilitated in part through the WorldFAIR week-long hackathon⁴ from 1-6 October 2023 focussed on the WorldFAIR Cross-Domain Implementation Framework (CDIF)⁵ to consider how our nanomaterials domain-specific solutions (such as the InstanceMap tool) can be extended to cover other domains, or mapped to the approaches used in other domains (such as biodiversity). This Dagstuhl Workshop created a unique opportunity for the case

¹ Lynch, I., Afantitis, A., Exner, T., & Papadiamantis, A. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D4.1) Nanomaterials domain-specific FAIRification mapping (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7887341>

² Lynch, I., & Afantitis, A. (2024). WorldFAIR (D4.2) FAIRification of nanoinformatics tools and models recommendations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10629631>

³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/831558>

⁴ <https://worldfair-project.eu/event/defining-a-core-metadata-framework-for-cross-domain-data-sharing-and-reuse/> at Schloss Dagstuhl, the Leibniz Centre for Informatics.

⁵ Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) Working Group, Richard, S., Gregory, A., Hodson, S., Fils, D., Kanjala, C., Bell, D., Winstanley, P., Edwards, M., Heus, P., Brickley, D., Rizzolo, F., Maxwell, L., Luis, G., Buttigieg, P. L., & Le Franc, Y. (2023). Cross Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF): Discovery Module (v01 draft for public consultation) (Version 01). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252564>

studies to present and discuss their individual approaches to data provenance related to events (e.g., sampling events, measurement events, data creation events), samples and occurrences, leading to a convergence in approach around the provenance ontology ([PROV-O](#)⁶), the Global Biodiversity Information Facility ([GBIF](#)) [New Data model](#), and the process for organising events and samples. In the nanomaterials context, we have also mapped an existing provenance ontology ([PROV-O](#)) and the GBIF approach to the community developed tools for capturing the evolution of nanomaterials along their lifecycle and in products, formalised via the Instance Map Tool (Exner et al., 2024).

While it has long been known that nanomaterials are very dynamic, this evolution of the materials during storage and sampling has not been systematically incorporated into materials provenance documentation which makes comparison of data challenging, as materials may have been handled differently and thus evolved differently, leading to different outcomes in terms of their toxicity.

The guidance and policy developed and presented here in WorldFAIR D4.3 will support increased implementation of best practice around complete documentation of provenance information about nanomaterials, their samples and the data arising from their production, use, testing, etc. These recommendations are being taken up by current nanosafety projects [MACRAME](#)⁷, [PINK](#)⁸, [CHIASMA](#)⁹ and [INSIGHT](#)¹⁰, among others, and will be further documented as a workflow for creation of FAIR digital objects¹¹ from nanomaterials datasets.

⁶ The PROV-O ontology <https://www.w3.org/TR/2013/REC-prov-o-20130430/>

⁷ MACRAME: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101092686>

⁸ PINK: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101137809>

⁹ CHIASMA: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101137613>

¹⁰ INSIGHT: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101137742>

¹¹ See for example: <https://fairdigitalobjectframework.org/>

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1. Introduction to the WorldFAIR nanomaterials case study

Work Package WP04 of WorldFAIR aims to increase the FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability) of nanomaterials datasets as well as computational models which utilise nanomaterials datasets to predict properties, interactions or effects of nanomaterials on living systems.

This initial focus on nanomaterials interactions and (eco)toxicity arises from the historical development of the field, whereby the dynamic nature of nanomaterials (Lowry et al., 2012), their designation by the European Commission as a key enabling technology, and the fact that they emerged after the EU Chemicals Legislation REACH (Registration, Evaluation and Authorisation of Chemicals)¹² had been developed and was coming into force, meaning that there was a very strong push to develop knowledge on the safety and sustainability of nanomaterials in parallel to development of application. Consequently, there has been a large volume of data generated relating to the toxicity and impacts of nanoscale materials, driving a need for FAIR data solutions for nanomaterials data, and considerable investment into the development of predictive *in silico* models to support the transition away from animal testing to *in silico* approaches.

Nanomaterials are a very broad category of materials, combining chemicals and materials features, and overlapping strongly with the emerging domain of advanced materials. Nanosafety is a very broad domain, covering exposure, toxicity and risk assessment and requires extensive characterisation of the pristine (as-produced) nanomaterials and their physical, chemical, biological and macromolecular transformations within the various environments in which they are present. Thus, the positioning of nanomaterials between Chemistry (WP03) and Geochemistry (WP05) in the WorldFAIR petal diagram¹³ is intentional, as there are strong overlaps of concepts and approaches with both, and solutions applicable to one of these domains are likely to be applicable to others also, leading to the potential for mutual learning and accelerated implementation of the FAIR concepts across these domains.

1.1. Context of the current Deliverable: provenance and persistence as key principles of FAIR

This is the third (and final) Deliverable from the WorldFAIR Nanomaterials case study work package, following on from previous deliverables on mapping of the FAIR landscape for nanomaterials (D4.1¹⁴) and best practice for FAIR nanoinformatics models (D4.2¹⁵). D4.3, presented here, complements and extends the previous two Deliverables, focussing in particular on provenance and persistence of nanomaterials data, considering both human and machine-actionable aspects.

¹² <https://echa.europa.eu/regulations/reach/understanding-reach>

¹³ <https://worldfair-project.eu/nanomaterials/>

¹⁴ WorldFAIR Deliverable D4.1: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7887341>

¹⁵ WorldFAIR Deliverable D4.2: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10629631>

“The term ‘data provenance’, sometimes called ‘data lineage’, refers to a documented trail that accounts for the origin of a piece of data and where it has moved from to where it is presently.”¹⁶ Data provenance is the core aspect of FAIR principle R1.2 whereby *(Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance*. This means that information about creators, source data, research questions or projects and other contextual information that is relevant for assessing possible reuse is required, as well as information about data lifecycle events and technical information about used software, protocols and methods, as defined in the PROV ontology¹⁷.

Persistent / unique identifiers (PIDs / UUIDs) can be used to support the creation of provenance metadata, for instance by creating PIDs for samples, sensors, instruments or workflows. Within the WorldFAIR nanomaterials case study context, this approach has been taken for generation of globally unique and persistent identifiers for nanomaterials that enable tracking of their environmental and biological transformations along the material life cycle, as described in WorldFAIR D4.1 (Lynch et al., 2023).

Persistence also relates to FAIR principle A2: *Metadata should be accessible even when the data is no longer available*, which also comes back to effective use of persistent identifiers as a core component of linked data (i.e., structured data which is interlinked with other data so it becomes more useful through semantic queries).

1.2. A brief primer on globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifiers (GUPRIs)

“PIDs, along with their accompanying metadata, are crucial enablers of the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). PIDs ensure that digital objects can be located, accessed, and reused by humans and machines alike, while metadata provides essential information about research objects, including their origin, content and format.”¹⁸

The FAIR Cookbook¹⁹ provides a summary of PIDs and approaches for minting them. Many of the core features of the research process have relatively well-standardised PIDs, including researcher IDs (ORCIDs), research institutes (RORs) and publications (DOIs from publishers), as shown schematically in Figure 1²⁰.

¹⁶ <https://www.nlm.gov/guides/data-glossary/data-provenance>

¹⁷ PROV-O: The PROV Ontology. Accessed July 30, 2020. <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

¹⁸ Chen, X. (2023) Making Research FAIR With a PID-centric Workflow. Presentation, 9 June. Edinburgh Open Research. <http://journals.ed.ac.uk/eor/article/view/8117>.

¹⁹ <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/content/recipes/findability/identifiers.html#fcb-find-identifiers>

²⁰ <https://projects.tib.eu/pid-service/en/persistent-identifiers/persistent-identifiers-pids/>

Figure 1: Examples of well-established and widely adopted PIDs. Source: TIB PID Competence Center. CC-BY 3.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>

More recently, efforts have been made to develop PIDs for research samples, such as International Generic Sample Numbers (IGSNs²¹) which were originally designed for geoscience samples but have begun to be used for a variety of biological and environmental sample types. Similarly, the mapping of PIDs in the FAIRsFAIR project (2019 - 2022) onto requirements for persistence and interoperability (Riungu-Kalliosaari et al., 2020) indicated that work is underway to develop PIDs for field sampling sites, and for instruments and sensors for measurement, as shown in Table 1.

In the nanomaterials case study context, PIDs are needed to identify specific nanomaterials and various approaches are emerging, such as the European Materials Registry (local identifiers for in-project use initially, see van Rijn et al., 2022), and the extension of the IUPAC International Chemical Identifier (InChI), which is a structure-based chemical identifier developed by IUPAC and the InChI Trust (see for example Heller et al., 2015) to represent the 3D complexity of nanomaterials via a NanoInChI (see Lynch et al., 2020). This is a standard identifier for chemical databases that facilitates effective information management across chemistry. to represent the composition and structure of nanomaterials (Lynch et al., 2020); although, as shown in the Appendix of this Deliverable, the current version of Nanomaterials InChI has evolved considerably since the initial publication.

²¹ IGSN identifiers: <https://datacite.org/igsn/>

Table 1: Contexts where emerging PID systems have been identified with examples of schemas and service providers. Reproduced from FAIRsFAIR Deliverable D2.4 (Riungu-Kalliosaari et al., 2020) and extended (**text in red**) based on information relevant to nanomaterials and toxicology, including where PIDs are needed but currently lacking.

Object type	PID scheme	Service providers (not all provide proxy or landing page, but these can be used to disambiguate and link information)
Organisation	DOI RoR ISNI GRID Ringgold IDs Wikidata ids EU VAT numbers LEI PSI OID	DOI : Crossref (no landing page) RoR : (community-led project) ISNI : International Agency Ltd. GRID: Digital Science solution RIN: Ringgold Inc Wikidata id: Wikimedia foundation LEI: Global Legal Entity Identifier Foundation (GLEIF) OID: ITU
Data repositories	DOI	DataCite Elixir/ University of Oxford
Projects	local identifier, accession number, RAiD	EU Project Identifiers RAiD ²² : Global consortium, now governed by ISO standard 23527:2022 . Like IGSN, RAiD is a partnership with DataCite who provide backend minting service.
Grants	DOI, PURL URI	DOI: CrossRef EU Project Identifiers
Software	DOI, SHA-1 hash, SWH, commit hash	Zenodo/DataCite, Software Heritage
Instrument, Device, Sensor, Platform, Research Facility	DOI, RRID, UUID	DataCite RRID: University of California DOI: Journal of large-scale research facilities JLSRF CHADA (materials characterisation metadata) ²³
Field Station /	deims id., IGSN	DEIMS (Dynamic Ecological Information Management)

²² <https://raid.org>; RAiD is currently being integrated with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) infrastructure via [FAIRCORE4EOSC](#).

²³ <https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/CWAs/ICT/cwa17815.pdf>

Field site		System - Site and dataset registry) IGSN: International Generic Sample Number ("feature of interest" and "Penultimate Feature of Interest" as per ISO 19156:2023)
Physical Sample or Object Nanomaterial or sample containing nanomaterials	Accession number, RRID, DOI, IGSN, URN Nanomaterial identifier	RRID: University of California IGSN: International Generic Sample Number ERM: European Registry of Materials (see van Rijn et al., 2020) NinChI: InChI for Nanomaterials (see Lynch et al., 2020 for early prototype) and AuxInfo²⁴ files associated with NInChIs (to be developed).
Endpoint / Assay identifier	Ontology terms but no PIDs	Need PIDs for assays, endpoints, cell lines / organisms etc.
AOP identifiers	AOP Wiki pathway numbers	Need PIDs for Key Events, Molecular Initiating events etc.

Areas that we have identified as not yet addressed in terms of PIDs, but which will be picked up over the coming year in the FAIR activities of the Partnership for Assessment of the Risks of Chemicals (PARC²⁵) in collaboration with the ELIXIR Toxicology Community²⁶, are shown in red at the bottom of Table 1, and include toxicology endpoint and assay identifiers, and identifiers for Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) and their constituent key events.

Two major dimensions of PIDs are their role in the management of research information and in the management of research data. The first is focussed on metadata and serves creating knowledge about the research at large, while the latter serves scientific purposes in expressing the structures of the data and managing the lifecycle and documentation to support things like the reproducibility and transparency of the research (Riungu-Kalliosaari et al., 2020).

²⁴ <https://www.inchi-trust.org/technical-faq-2/#11.1>

²⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101057014>

²⁶ <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/toxicology>

1.3. Reflections from the WorldFAIR Dagstuhl breakout session on ‘Events, Samples and Occurrences’

As part of the 2023 Dagstuhl workshop on the WorldFAIR CDIF²⁷, several of the WorldFAIR case studies came together to identify commonalities and reach consensus on the topic of ‘Events, occurrences and samples’. Our working brief was as follows:

“Many domains have similar approaches for organising their data: events become the subject of measurements. Often, samples are a critical aspect of such approaches. The act of measurement – the occurrence – is often an important focus. This type of data description – and the description of relevant data collection and sampling events – has implications for what constitutes sufficient provenance information. These elements are combined in different ways across domains, and yet bear many similarities. The goal of this group [participating in the Dagstuhl workshop was] to identify similarities across domains, and to consider the requirements for exchange of this information across domains boundaries. This discussion [was] exploratory [...], but [drew] upon the models and standards which address these topics”.²⁸

Among the standards considered were the GBIF Unified Model (as described in [WorldFAIR D9.1](#))²⁹, the combined Open Geospatial Consortium and ISO/TC 211 Observations, Measurements and Samples Standard (OGC 20-082r4 / ISO 19156:2023)³⁰, the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership’s (OMOP) Common Data Model³¹, and others.”

Our objective was to try and better understand how we can improve the way we communicate the contextual, provenance information of data to help people outside our domain reuse that data. In particular there is a lot of assumed knowledge that specialists in a field have that is not apparent to specialists from other fields, which can hamper effective data re-use across domains. For example, across domains there are a set of categories of process, and this information needs to be communicated for data to be reused. This can assist reuse, reproducibility, and an understanding of data quality. Our contention from the workshop is that it is helpful to think about three categories of concepts and information that need to be communicated:

1. Contextual/provenance information in the creation of the data;
2. Unit / object of interest;
3. Conceptual variables.

²⁷ <https://worldfair-project.eu/event/defining-a-core-metadata-framework-for-cross-domain-data-sharing-and-reuse/>

²⁸

<https://ddi-alliance.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/DDI4/pages/2946531350/2023+Defining+a+Core+Metadata+Framework+for+Cross-Domain+Data+Sharing+and+Reuse>

²⁹ <https://www.gbif.org/new-data-model>

³⁰ <https://www.ogc.org/standard/om/>

³¹ <https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization/>

A key feature of the WorldFAIR nanomaterials case study that differentiates it from the Chemistry, Geochemistry, Biodiversity and Agricultural Biodiversity case studies in WorldFAIR - and that emerged during the discussions of the 'Events, Samples and Occurrences' workshop session - is the distinction between the observatory nature of the other case studies (observing the occurrence of chemicals in the environment, the occurrence of a pollination event in a field, the presence or absence of eDNA in the environment as evidence of a species being present or not), versus the intentionality of the nanomaterials studied, whereby nanomaterials are intentionally synthesised to exploit their properties for a range of applications, and when studying their properties or toxicity they are intentionally added into the test systems in order to probe how systems respond to these additions. Thus, each of the case studies considered how the core concepts listed above apply to their context, and refined their understanding as needed.

An example of the research process in the nanomaterials and chemistry WorldFAIR case studies, using the categories of concepts described above, is presented (as there is considerable overlap between these two domains). In this example, we took the intentional synthesis of a gold nanomaterial with a specific size and surface charge, and its characterisation, to confirm that the produced nanomaterial was indeed the intended one, through size and surface charge measurements by dynamic light scattering.

1. Provenance concepts:

- a. Change events - where a chemical reaction occurs or something is done to a sample (e.g. heating, applying a current, hitting with a light or electron beam as part of a characterisation method, etc.)
- b. Data events - events where data is generated (e.g. the scattering of the light or electrons during a nanomaterials characterisation measurement results in data regarding the scattering angles and amount of light reaching the detector.)
- c. Analysis / interpretation events - whereby the nanomaterial median size and surface charge are calculated from the light scattering and zeta potential measurements, respectively to give a size and size distribution, and an overall surface charge number.

2. Unit type / object of interest:

- a. Here the object of interest is the synthesised nanomaterial and its physico-chemical characteristics (properties which are measured under a specific set of conditions, as shown in Figure 2a), specifically the size and surface charge. We note that size and surface charge are ensemble measurements, giving the median value over the set of nano-objects present in the system, since a sample of nanomaterial is actually a collection of nano-objects, as defined in the CODATA-VAMAS Universal Description System for nanomaterials (2015) and shown schematically in Figure 2(b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. Concepts of (a) nanomaterials' extrinsic properties that are dependent on the surrounding conditions and (b) a nanomaterial sample as a collection of nano-objects, thus leading to a medium measurement of radius or diameter (in nm) and a distribution around that, for example size and size distribution, and medium surface charge and surface charge range (in mV).

3. Conceptual variable:

- a. The *activities* of observing, sampling, and actuating, each target some *feature of interest* by either changing its state or revealing its properties, each follows some *procedure*, and each is carried out by some object or *agent*. “Actuation” is the process of putting something into action or motion (see Figure 3).

In the context of nanomaterials (and chemicals) we can envisage a series of actuation events including:

- **Synthesis of a nanomaterial**, which itself may have several actuation steps such as dispersion of reactants, mixing and heating, adding further reactants, freeze-drying, etc. Indeed, it has been suggested that as reactions get increasingly complex, and materials have more components, that there is a need for an ontology of materials synthesis terms in order to annotate synthesis reactions (as shown in Figure 4), and to move towards more machine-actionable descriptions of materials synthesis processes (Kim et al., 2019). The proposed ontology includes a controlled vocabulary consisting of named entities: materials, operations (i.e., actions performed by experimenters - these would be Actuators in the SOSA ontology - see Janowicz et al., 2019), numbers, units, unit types (e.g., temperature), apparatuses, descriptive words (e.g., powder), and reaction conditions. Some of these entity types may be linked to others in a specific fashion: for example, amounts may only be linked to materials, and reaction conditions may only be linked to operations. The key detail in our ontology is that the “backbone” of a synthesis is a linked chain of in-lab operations. For example, a typical solid-state synthesis route may contain the operations, “mix, grind, sinter, cool.” The structure of such an ontology implies that, at the highest level of abstraction, the critical information to communicate is the precise sequence of actions that an experimenter performed on the materials.
- **Physico-chemical characterisation of the nanomaterial:** Characterisation events for various physico-chemical properties (composition, size, shape, surface charge, etc.) as per the specified study design / need. Each characterisation method has its own protocol for sample preparation, its own measurement principle, etc. In the case of nanomaterials characterisation, these can be documented using the CHADA standard (CWA 17815:2021)³².
- **Data event:** Some aspect of the signal is recorded as raw data. The magnitude of the signal is generally of interest, along with other possible characteristics (distribution, colour, etc.). Measuring instruments may capture original signals, such as light scattering, and many instruments include on-board software that provides some initial processing and presents signal output as relative to control samples, etc.

³² <https://www.cencenelec.eu/news-and-events/news/2024/workshop/2024-04-22-nano/>

Figure 3: Example of an annotated materials synthesis process, indicating the key steps and operations (or actuations in the context of this deliverable) in light blue in the figure, consisting of “mixed”, “put”, “filled”, “maintained” and “cooled” as part of the synthesis workflow. While the details of the synthesis are not important, the figure shows also numeric values (in green), units (in orange), materials descriptors (e.g., powder, solution) and apparatus descriptors in purple, and chemicals in navy blue, apparatus types (e.g., autoclave) in red, and apparatus property types (e.g., capacity, total volume) in yellow. Reproduced from Kim et al., 2019.

- NMs impacts on living systems.** A key feature of the nanomaterials case study that was not obviously the case for the others (except possibly geochemistry) was the intentional addition of nanomaterials into a living test system or ecosystem in order to explore the impacts of the nanomaterial on the system (toxicity or ecotoxicity assessment) and the impacts of the system on the nanomaterials properties (environmental transformations, biodegradation, bioaccumulation etc.).

Figure 4: The core structure of the Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator (SOSA) ontology, showing relationship to PROV-O. Reproduced from Janowicz et al., 2019.

2. Materials and sample provenance as part of data provenance trails

2.1. Cross-domain alignment

A major outcome from the WorldFAIR Dagstuhl workshop was that all of the participating case studies (Chemistry, Nanomaterials, Geochemistry, Biodiversity, Agricultural Biodiversity and Cultural Heritage) were able to map themselves and their approaches to the Unified Model proposed in the WorldFAIR Biodiversity case study (see WorldFAIR [D9.1](#)), which is shown schematically in Figure 5.

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Figure 5: The GBIF Unified Model³³ showing the types of events (Actuation, Observation and Interpretation) in purple, the various entities (materials, protocols, digital entities) in cream, and the agent (researcher, curator etc.) shown in orange. An assertion (hypothesis, interpretation) appears in green and is also noted in the metadata model.

³³ Miller, J., Robertson, T., & Wiczorek, J. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D9.1) Data standard for sharing ecological and environmental monitoring data documented for community review (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7849241>

A key feature of the 20-year experience of GBIF is the approach of first working with experimental researchers to generate a narrative, using a use-case template. The example discussed at the WorldFAIR Dagstuhl workshop is shown in Figure 6.

In every use case documented by GBIF, the conceptual and data publishing models are built around the fundamental concept of an event - something that happened within some place during some period of time, optionally described by a protocol. This is based on two important factors: the first is a synthesis of preliminary research at the beginning of the project to understand how scientific physical entities, observations, processes and the relationships between them tend to be successfully expressed in a wide range of high-level foundational models and ontologies³⁴, and the second factor supporting an event-centric conceptual model is that it is extremely flexible. It has already been demonstrated to provide the capacity to publish rich hierarchical, ecological datasets, using the Darwin Core Event schema as the core of a Darwin Core Archive, and the GBIF team have been able to use it effectively as the foundation for every use case encountered³⁵.

Figure 6. Diagram showing the progression of the Unified Model development process. Source: GBIF, WorldFAIR [D9.1](#), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7849241>.

2.2. Typical observations in nanosafety research

Guided by the successful implementation of the Unified Model in GBIF and the results of the intensive collaborations with the Chemistry, Geochemistry, Biodiversity, Agricultural Biodiversity and Cultural Heritage Case Studies as described above, the provenance information documentation guidelines, developed in the WP09 nanomaterials case study work package and proposed to the NanoSafety community (as well as, in an extended form, to the new Horizon Europe funded projects

³⁴ <https://ipt.gbif.org/manual/en/ipt/latest/best-practices-sampling-event-data>

³⁵

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1QpXwole_j32QZAg6dddqOrAB5OOdqVJKdoKKz06CK-o/edit#heading=h.ap9414stalys

addressing the topics of Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) and Advanced Materials) are based on the three categories of concepts and information:

1. Contextual/provenance information on the creation of data, with its sub-categories of
 - a. Change events;
 - b. Data events;
 - c. Analysis / interpretation events.
2. Unit / object of interest.
3. Conceptual variables defining the phenomenon being measured/observed.

In this section, the first category will be discussed, while section 2.3 covers the object of interest (category 2, in the nanomaterials case study this is nanomaterials) and its dependency on category 1. Full coverage of all information needed to describe the vast number of measurements used in nanosafety research alone (category 3), which is dramatically increased when including performance and environmental, economic and social sustainability aspects in a SSbD approach and moving to the larger group of Advanced Materials, is beyond the scope of this deliverable report. However, the importance of including method descriptions, measuring principles, protocols and standard operating procedures (SOPs) as part of the (meta)data was already stressed in WorldFAIR Deliverables 4.1 and 4.2. Corresponding FAIR resources like standards and (meta)data schemas are reviewed in section 2.4.

Table 2 lists typical events observed in typical measurement studies, which need to be documented as contextual/provenance information, as agreed by the Case Studies present at the WorldFAIR Dagstuhl workshop. This can be separated into three parts: (a) definition of the study, (b) events before and during sample collection and (c) preparation for and execution of the experiment.

The usefulness of separating the steps of an experiment into sample preparation, measurement and data processing was already recognised by the nanosafety community and implemented, for example in the ACEnano Knowledge Infrastructure³⁶ for grouping protocols and structure reported data of physicochemical characterisation experiments. However, in contrast to the biodiversity and geochemistry cases presented by others in the workshop, nanomaterials and more general chemicals of interest are intentionally produced materials, of which the properties are dependent on the production processes and, especially for nanomaterials, all the intentional or unintentional changes which happen between production and measurement. This ability of engineered nanomaterials to change characteristics over time (even during storage as shown by Izak-Nau et al, 2015) and based on properties of their environment, presents a unique challenge for evaluating their potential environmental and human risks (Rauscher et al., 2017; Clausen et al., 2018).

³⁶ <https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/release-of-acenano-knowledge-warehouse/>

Table 2: Application of the WorldFAIR consensus approach on “Events” as applied to a measurement event involving the characterisation of a physical property of a nanomaterial.

Activity	Outcomes	Type	Connected entities
Study design	Reference question, hypothesis, study scope, protocols	Interpretation	Researcher (agent)
Chemical / material transformation event	Material of some chemical composition (May be from a natural event or intentional exposure or recipe)	Event (feature of study interest)	Time OR Researcher (agent - intentional)
Sample collection	Entity of study material acquired, non-chemical characterization	Actuation	Researcher (agent)
Steps below happen during a chemical analysis of a sample			
Sample preparation	Specified aliquot of material dissolved or suspended in measurement medium	[Actuation] (not the feature of interest)	Sample (material) Analyst (agent)
Measurement	Instrumentation inputs	Actuation	Sample (material) Analyst (agent) Instrument (agent)
Data collection	Raw data files	Observation	Instrument (agent)
Data processing	Processed data files	Actuation	Reference data (e.g., controls)
Data analysis	Assertion	Interpretation	Reported information on chemical identification and property values (e.g., concentration of chemical of interest in sample)
Link back to original research study / context	Assertion	Interpretation	Researcher asserts if this supports their original study / hypothesis

This context dependence requires, on the one hand, distinction between extrinsic nanomaterial properties that can change as the surroundings change and intrinsic nanomaterial properties which are not affected by the surroundings. On the other hand, and perhaps even more important, it might not be possible to define a lifecycle stage of a nanomaterial just by its chemical constitution and physico-chemical characterisation of the pristine material, since some of the modification can lead to chemically ill-defined species (e.g., dissolution, partial oxidations, and random surface modifications). Thus, the time between synthesis and initial characterisation and toxicity or analysis,

as well as changes in conditions of the surrounding medium, are important to document - although this is not routinely reported in the literature (Hendron et al., 2015).

Table 3: Application of the WorldFAIR (consensus) approach from the Dagstuhl workshop to “Events” to a nanomaterials synthesis, characterisation and ecotoxicity evaluation. *Actuation Events* are indicated in purple, the *Protocols* underpinning the actuation events are indicated in brown text, the *Assertion(s)* arising from the actuation events are indicated in red text, and the resulting *Digital Entity* is indicated in orange text.

Activity	Outcomes	Type	Connected entities
Study design	Reference question, hypothesis, study scope, protocols	Interpretation	Researcher (agent)
Chemical / material synthesis reaction	Intentionally produced entity (NM/Ada) as object for subsequent analysis / use	<i>Actuation Event</i> (to generate the feature of interest) <i>Protocol</i> <i>Assertion</i>	Sample (material) Researcher (agent) Report (e.g. SDS, Specification)
Sample Transport	Physical movement of sample location (Change to metadata not sample)	[Actuation] (not the feature of interest)	Researcher (agent) Sample (NM/chemical)
Sample storage / ageing	Period with potential for intentional or unintentional changes (Change to metadata not sample)	<i>Actuation Event</i> <i>Protocol</i> <i>Assertion</i>	Sample (NM/chemical)
Change of environment	Transformation including biotransformations resulting from transfer from one environment into another	<i>Actuation Event</i> with <i>Protocol</i> <i>Assertion</i>	Researcher (agent) Sample (NM/chemical) Organism(s) (agent)
Sample collection	Entity of study material acquired, non-chemical characterisation	Actuation	Researcher (agent)
Sample preparation	Specified aliquot of material dissolved or suspended in measurement medium	[Actuation] (not the feature of interest) <i>Protocol</i> <i>Assertion</i>	Sample (material) Analyst (agent)
Intentional addition of material to system of study	Established the basis for “interaction” and “effect” that can be observed / measured	<i>Actuation Event</i> with <i>Protocol</i> <i>Assertion</i>	Researcher (agent) Sample (NM/chemical) Organism (acting as a biosensor)
Measurement	Instrumentation inputs	<i>Actuation Event</i> with <i>Protocol</i> <i>Digital entity</i>	Sample (material) Analyst (agent) Instrument (agent)

Data collection	Raw data files	Observation with Protocol Digital entity (instrument software template)	Instrument (agent)
Data processing	Processed data files	Actuation Event Digital entity (data template)	Analyst (agent) Reference data (e.g., controls)
Data analysis	Assertion	Interpretation with Assertion Digital entity (data template, Reference spectra / peak assignment)	Reported information on the specific physico-chemical characteristic of the NM of interest
Link back to original research study / context	Assertion	Interpretation -> Publication	Researcher asserts if this supports their original study / hypothesis

Consequently, Bear et al. (2016) suggested that the essential history of a set of particles needs to be reported as provenance information that tells the origin or source of a batch of nano-objects along with information related to handling and any changes that may have taken place since it was originated, decreasing the extent of particle variability and the lack of reproducibility observed by many researchers.

To highlight the importance of documenting the nanomaterials' history (also referred to in environmental risk assessment literature as recording the nanomaterials' fate in the environment, as shown schematically in 7 where taking the fate information in reverse provides the history of the nanomaterial) to understand the results of the experiment, reproduce it and compare it to other experiments, including evaluation of the sameness or similarity of the nanomaterials under investigation, the activities describing the events before the experiment as well as during sample preparation should be made more specific for the nanomaterial/nanosafety domain compared to the listing in Table 2.

A starting point is shown in Table 3 with activities like synthesis, transport, storage and exposure added, which can be further refined based on the requirements for the neighbouring fields of materials characterisation and modelling as well as the emerging fields of SSbD and Advanced Materials.

2.3. Organisation of material, sample and data provenance trails as Instance Maps

As discussed in the previous section, a nanomaterial state and its observable properties are inseparably connected to its history. For investigations looking at later life-cycle stages of the materials like exposure from nano-containing / nano-enabled products or end-of-life scenarios like incineration or land-filling and associated exposure, these interlinks can become very complex and

hard to understand when encoded in all-covering data structure or even when trying to follow the corresponding publication.

This became obvious in the data curation efforts of the NanoInformatics Knowledge Commons database (Amos et al., 2021) tasked with systematically retrofitting experimental data from published literature describing nanomaterials mesocosm studies in order to capture the nanomaterial transformations in a manner that sufficiently includes surrounding medium characteristics, thus representing both intrinsic and extrinsic properties of the studied material (Hendren et al., 2015).

To facilitate the data curation and provide an overall representation of a study, the concept of the “nanomaterial instances and instance maps” was introduced covering the transformations that nano-scaled materials underwent in environmental and biological compartments (Amos et al., 2024). Instances were designed to capture the necessary metadata needed to describe a material and its surrounding medium in mesocosm experiments, while keeping the sequence of transformations intact. Material transformations are tracked through connected instances.

The benefits quickly emerged of a visual representation for study design to guide researchers in what characterisation and system metadata was needed for complete reporting of nanosafety studies. Researchers and complete project consortia used instance maps independently of the NIKC for purposes beyond data curation. This adoption was further enabled by provision of a specialised tool for creating instance maps developed in the NanoCommons project and then further optimised in different follow-up projects, including WorldFAIR. Detailed description of the tool and application to nanomaterial synthesis, monitoring of nanomaterial transformation in complex environmental media, quality assessment and control, human immunotoxicity assessment, and even planning and refining material and data workflows in large collaborative projects is available in Exner et al. (2023) and Punz et al. (2024).

However, all these applications see the instance maps mainly as a tool to follow the work performed in the study - from preparation of the material or sample collection over the different transformation steps to measurement of different safety endpoints (see Figure 7). By using the instance maps as a way to organise the data collection and structure the (meta)data, which is now possible using the improved features of the instance map tool, they become a FAIR-enabling resource (specifically a provenance tracking service as defined in the FAIR Implementation Profile Ontology³⁷), and are especially suited to cover material, sample and data provenance trails by following the maps backwards from the measurement to the origin of the material (see also Figure 7).

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<https://peta-pico.github.io/FAIR-nanopubs/fip/index-en.html#https://w3id.org/fair/fip/terms/Provenance-Tracking-Service>

Figure 7: Part of an instance map (adapted from Exner et al., 2023 and Punz et al., 2024]) to demonstrate how it can be used to describe the fate of a nanomaterial by visualising intentional and unintentional transformations occurring, e.g. when transferring the material from one (biological) medium into another (arrow to the right). Additionally, the map can be used to organise the data collected for all the individual instances and transformation and, in this way, provides provenance trails of the material and samples. These are then integrated as part of the metadata for the study (arrow to the left).

To show how this collection of full data provenance trails can be realised with instance maps, Figure 8 shows a more comprehensive, although artificial map.

To obtain all relevant (meta)data for the experiment on an unspecified safety endpoint of a polymer/carbon nanotube dispersion on the low right side of the figure, information on the sample preparation, measurement and data processing (and additional activities of the “preparation for and execution of the experiment” category of Table 3) will be reported by partner 1. This data will include a reference to information from the material producer on how the samples were prepared and shipped to partner 1 completing the sample provenance trails for this experiment. However, this is not enough to completely characterise the material in the samples and thus, the information on the full production process back to the raw materials are added as material provenance trail

(middle part). Two additional safety endpoints needed to be determined for the anti foaming agent used in the production and the sample provenance trails for these experiments (left part) become part of the material provenance.

All this collected information, potentially enriched by additional public available data (with provenance information) on the raw materials (e.g. from safety data sheets), replaces or complements a chemical/structural description of materials, where such a description is not possible or sufficient as discussed above, and should become part of the metadata and the data provenance trail.

Using instance maps for guiding this process has the additional benefit, besides clearly showing what information is needed, that clear handover points are defined, where a downstream process can rely on metadata including provenance provided by an upstream process. In this way, the material producer can collect all information already in a structured and preferably harmonised format during production, i.e. on-the-fly, before they send out the samples for testing. Partner 1 and 2 then just have to add their information and complete the material, samples and data provenance trails by linking to the information from the material producer. In Figure 8, only the production of the material and the characterisation of the presine material are covered. If the goal of the study is to investigate later life-cycle stages like use scenarios, exposure to the environment or end-of-life situations, the instance map can just be extended and the additional provenance data added without the need to modify any of the existing parts.

2.4 Reusing (meta)data standards and information provided by public registries

Instance maps are, as discussed above, a kind of road map of how to reach all provenance data relevant for data generated for a specific life-cycle stage. However, they are not the means to store the provenance information. Instead they are linking to (meta)data files or data packages, where this information is stored together with other metadata fields and the actual data.

To keep the advantage of separating the complex study into independent pieces, the nodes of the map have to be assigned to and integrated into the provenance concepts as described in Section 2.2 and, to the degree possible, aligned to existing metadata standards.

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Figure 8: Example instance map showing the production of a material (centre block) which was shipped to three laboratories for different characterisation experiments. The arrows symbolise how the maps can be travelled backwards to access all information on the history of the samples and the material (provenance tracking) and how this will be provided as metadata for the unambiguous specification of the material and its life-cycle stage under investigation in a specific experiment.

Figure 9 shows that there are multiple, quite trivial, mapping steps between instance maps notes and the concepts and categories building the provenance trails (as discussed in Section 2.2 and already implemented in the GBIF Unified Model). ‘Materials’, ‘Media’ and their collection into instances correspond directly to ‘MaterialEntity’, ‘Raw Data’ and ‘Processed Data’, and map to ‘Digital Entity’ and different transformations covered in the different types of Protocols available in the Instance Map Tool to ‘Protocols’ in the GBIF Unified Model schema.

There is still some debate on how the ‘Properties’ nodes should be used in instance maps but they are most often seen as containers for complete measurements and can therefore be seen as equivalent to ‘Observation Events’. The only provenance metadata category completely missing in the instance maps is ‘Agent’. This is not unexpected since, as stressed above, the instance maps are not a way to store the provenance data but a way to access it, when used as one part of the data management system and combined with an appropriate (meta)data storage solution.

However, to support cross-domain interoperability, the harmonised description of the provenance data (or at least the parts in common across the disciplines) in the (meta)data files is essential and should be based, as much as possible, on existing standards. PROV³⁸ is a well-established standard for data provenance documentation and is recommended by the cross-domain interoperability framework (Gregory and Hodson, 2023).

A visualisation of the basic data model of PROV is shown in Figure 10 showing very high similarity to the GBIF Unified Model shown in Figure 5 and a similar mapping to the instance maps nodes as shown in Figure 9 can be performed as shown in Figure 11. Thus, material and sample provenance can be also described using PROV as the underlying metadata standard, which is not unexpected since we defined these kinds of provenance trails as part or as specific subtypes of data provenance trails.

³⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-overview/>

Figure 9: Mapping of nodes presenting different research outputs and actions in the instance maps to the provenance concepts established in GBIF and used as bases for defining the nanomaterial provenance trails. The specific details are not important, rather that the concepts map well to one another and can be easily linked.

Figure 10: Visualisation of the basic data model of PROV (reproduced from the PROV primer³⁹).

Figure 11: Mapping of the components of the PROV data model onto instance map nodes.

To make this Deliverable understandable without the need to consult other sources, we will replicate here the important concepts of PROV, defining the entries in the figure as well as related entries in the data model. The number used in the original document is used to make it easier to

³⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/2013/NOTE-prov-primer-20130430/>

refer back for more details during implementation of the guideline during ongoing and future FAIRification activities:

- **2.1 Entities:** In PROV, physical, digital, conceptual, or other kinds of things are called entities. Examples of such entities are a web page, a chart, and a spellchecker. Provenance records can describe the provenance of entities, and an entity's provenance may refer to many other entities. For example, a document D is an entity whose provenance refers to other entities such as a chart inserted into D, and the dataset that was used to create that chart. Entities may be described as having different attributes and be described from different perspectives. For example, document D as stored in my file system, the second version of document D, and D as an evolving document, are three distinct entities for which we may describe provenance.
- **2.2 Activities:** Activities are how entities come into existence and how their attributes change to become new entities, often making use of previously existing entities to achieve this. They are dynamic aspects of the world, such as actions, processes, etc. For example, if the second version of document D was generated by a translation from the first version of the document in another language, then this translation is an activity.
- **2.3 Usage and Generation:** Activities generate new entities. For example, writing a document brings the document into existence, while revising the document brings a new version into existence. Activities also make use of entities. For example, revising a document to fix spelling mistakes uses the original version of the document as well as a list of corrections. Generation does not always occur at the end of an activity, and an activity may generate entities part-way through. Likewise, usage does not always occur at the beginning of an activity.
- **2.4 Agents and Responsibility:** An agent takes a role in an activity such that the agent can be assigned some degree of responsibility for the activity taking place. An agent can be a person, a piece of software, an inanimate object, an organisation, or other entities that may be ascribed responsibility. When an agent has some responsibility for an activity, PROV says the agent was associated with the activity, where several agents may be associated with an activity and vice-versa. Consider a chart displaying some statistics regarding crime rates over time in a linear regression. To represent the provenance of that chart, we could state that the person who created the chart was an agent involved in its creation, and that the software used to create the chart was also an agent involved in that activity. An agent may be acting on behalf of others, e.g. an employee on behalf of their organisation, and we can express such chains of responsibility in the provenance.
- **2.5 Roles:** A role is a description of the function or the part that an entity played in an activity. Roles specify the relationship between an entity and an activity, i.e. how the activity used or generated the entity. Roles also specify how agents are involved in an activity, qualifying their participation in the activity or specifying for what aspect of it each agent was responsible. For example, an agent may play the role of "editor" in an activity that uses one entity in the role of "document to be edited" and another in the role of "addition to be

made to the document", to generate a further entity in the role of "edited document". Roles are application specific, so PROV does not define any particular roles.

- **2.6 Plans:** Activities may follow pre-defined procedures, such as recipes, tutorials, instructions, or workflows. PROV refers to these, in general, as plans, and allows the description that a plan was followed, by agents, in executing an activity.

From the examples given in these definitions, it becomes clear that some of the categories are exactly transferable from more standard data types and provenance trails to materials and samples. Thus, documentation of these can be based on the PROV ontology and many services providing unique identifiers for persons and organisations like ORCID⁴⁰ and ROR⁴¹ or references to external documents and other digital objects (DOI).

We expect that collection of such data can become increasingly automated based on the above-mentioned services as well as ongoing work performed as part of the OpenAIRE Graph project⁴², which provides a unified access to the different services as well as aggregates everything together to show relationships. Figure 12 shows how connections in the OpenAIRE Graph can be used to fill provenance information e.g., by providing the organisational information to a person acting as an Agent in a specific Activity or providing unique identifiers to entities, which have been registered in OpenAIRE as research products.

However, the figure also shows where the inclusion of material and sample transformation activities as part of data provenance requires extension to the PROV ontology and OpenAIRE Graph semantic representation. Many different activities have been defined during the adaptation of the GBIF Unified Model to nanomaterials and it might be necessary to make these more specific, based on feedback from use cases of the provenance guidelines presented here. Since these are domain-specific, these additions should best be added to domain ontologies like eNanoMapper, from which some of the concepts are already available and which will also be used for annotating other (meta)data fields.

⁴⁰ <https://orcid.org/>

⁴¹ <https://ror.org/>

⁴² <https://graph.openaire.eu/>

Need for improvement of semantic coverage of materials and samples
 → following GBIF approach

Figure 12: Data entries in the OpenAIRE Graph (<https://graph.openaire.eu/>), which as shown here, can be used to fill in provenance metadata according to the PROV data model, as well as gaps in the semantic representation of both OpenAIRE Graph and PROV, which need to be closed by domain-specific ontology development. Source: <https://graph.openaire.eu/>.

3. Conclusions

The nanomaterials safety community has long been aware of the need for provenance information, about the shelf-lives of nanomaterials (and similar challenges hold for advanced materials) but the lack of tools and resources to support easy documentation of material and sample provenance and feed these into data provenance workflows, has hampered systematic implementation of good practice both by experimentalists and data managers / data repositories.

The goal of D4.3 was to help overcome these barriers and provide workflows and tools for documentation of provenance information regarding the nanomaterials themselves, samples (and formulations) utilising these nanomaterials and the characterisation and (eco)toxicity data generated on the materials dispersions / formulations / samples. The Deliverable also addresses the need for persistence of this information, particularly the metadata, and provides good practice on how to implement this.

A key learning from the current Deliverable report is that since nanomaterials and other WorldFAIR domains were able to map successfully to the GBIF Unified model structure for metadata, uptake of the recommendations made for nanomaterials in this deliverable report D4.3 within the nanomaterials community - or beyond to the contiguous communities of materials modelling, Advanced Materials, Safe and Sustainable by Design and others - ensures greater interoperability with those other domains of practice.

4. Recommendations

Based on the information collated and summarised in this report, the following recommendations are provided for **the nanomaterials research community and its stakeholders including industry and regulators, and database developers**.

4.1. Policy recommendations to support complete provenance information for (nano)materials data

- Adopt the **Event-based approach** developed collaboratively by a subset of WorldFAIR Case Studies to nanomaterials, sample and data provenance metadata. This approach maps well to the emerging instance map approach that has been developed and promoted in the nanosafety community offering convergence of the existing approaches, and enables the complexity of nanomaterials transformations and the intentionality of adding nanomaterials to systems and assessing the system responses to be captured and documented. *Target: Database developers.*

- Support the widespread adoption of the Instance Map Tool and the provenance workflows for materials, samples and data to become a standard, for example via a CEN workshop agreement⁴³ or other relevant approach. *Target: Regulators and industry.*
- Develop a community-wide international platform such as GBIF for the nanomaterials and advanced materials communities, supported by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, to support the collective development and implementation of data standards for materials. The GBIF approach offers an excellent model and has been transformative for the FAIRness of Biodiversity data. *Target: Materials and contiguous research communities, funders.*

4.2. Community action recommendations to support to support complete provenance information for (nano)materials data

- Integrate the provenance considerations described in this deliverable into research workflows through adoption of the Instance Map tool, and the development of a range of use cases to demonstrate its effectiveness. *Target: Materials and contiguous research communities, database developers.*
- Develop a range of data provenance trails and workflows as reference materials for use by the nanomaterials and advanced materials community, and define a set of “event” definitions for materials synthesis and characterisation. These can then be formalised alongside the emerging Materials synthesis ontology to support machine-actionability of materials synthesis data. *Target: Materials and contiguous research communities, standardisation and international organisations (e.g., CEN/CENELEC, OECD).*
- Develop the AuxInfo for the Nanomaterials InChI to include relevant provenance information in the second iteration of the standard extension to InChI. *Target: Materials and contiguous research communities, InChI Trust and IUPAC.*
- Develop use cases in existing nanomaterials and safe and sustainable by design Horizon Europe-funded projects including MACRAME, PINK, INSIGHT and CHIASMA. *Target: Materials and contiguous research communities*
- Provide user guides, tutorials and other training materials suitable for all users, regardless of their prior experience or technical competence, to enable the widest possible uptake of the approach for documentation of materials and data provenance. *Target: Materials and contiguous research communities, standardisation and international organisations.*

⁴³ A CEN/CENELEC Workshop Agreement (CWA) is an agreement, developed and approved by a CEN/CENELEC Workshop and owned by CEN/CENELEC as a publication, which reflects the consensus of identified individuals/organisations responsible for its contents. A CWA is voluntary, and should not be considered as legal advice authoritatively endorsed. <https://web.archive.org/web/20080918222123/http://www.cen.eu/cenorm/sectors/sectors/iss/cen+workshop+agreements/index.asp>

4.3. Database specific recommendations to support complete provenance information for nanomaterials data

- Database owners need to make provision for materials transformations and evolution, linked to the initially manufactured samples - this was implemented for example in the NanoCommons Knowledge Base (Maier et al., 2023), and is the basis for Instance Maps (Exner et al., 2024), which document every step where a transformation of the nanomaterial may occur (e.g., during storage, upon dispersion, upon exposure to cells or organisms, following uptake into the cell / organism etc.). *Target: Database developers / owners.*
- The nanomaterials community need to work with database owners to increase awareness of the need to document nanomaterials batch and lot numbers, opening dates of nanomaterials vials, potential impacts from shipping and storage of materials and other transformations on the nature and properties of the sample in order to enhance data harmonisation and re-usability. *Target: Materials research community and database developers.*
- Adopt best practice from geochemistry where samples extracted from specific sites need to have the entire provenance chain documented and linked to subsequent chemical and physical analyses. *Target: Materials research community and database developers.*

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